

IPBES BBA Chapter 6, data management report - A systematic review of governments' actions / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (Section 6.3)

Code: IPBES_BBA_CH6_DMR_government_actors

Versioning 03: (26.03.2026)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12787400

Project Leader

Mi Sun Park (mpark@snu.ac.kr)

Researchers

Syed Mohazri Bin Syed Hazari (klytomb@outlook.com)

Caroline van Leenders (Caroline.vanleenders@rvo.nl)

Data Curator

Alina Vera Paz (tsu.bizbiodiversity@gmail.com)

Description

This review corresponds to Chapter 6 of the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment. This review was conducted to describe actions by governments related to the measurement of businesses' dependences and impacts on biodiversity. The review focuses on how these measures of dependence and impact on biodiversity inform decision making for biodiversity conservation and management. It collected scientific results for developing policies or policy instruments that promote business actions for conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. The literature search was conducted from 9 May 2024 to 2 June 2024 using SCOPUS, one of the largest citation databases for peer-reviewed multidisciplinary scientific literature.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Search of articles indexed in Scopus
- **Search languages:** Abstract, title, and keyword in English
- **Search engine:** Scopus
- **Search Date:** 9 May 2024 to 2 June 2024
- **Search terms (R1):**

("biodiversity" AND "impact*") AND ("government*") AND ("business" OR "enterprise*" OR "compan*" OR "firm*") AND ("subsid*" OR "PES*" OR "payment for ecosystem service*" OR "REDD*" OR "fund*" OR "tax*" OR "fee*" OR "incentive*")

This search aims to collect the cases including scientific results about biodiversity policies to promote business with economic and financial instruments. Therefore, the search strings are a combination of four topics: biodiversity, impact, government and economic and financial instruments.

- **Sample extracted:** 114 papers (A)
- **Location of key papers:** IPBES_BBA_6.4_07-2024_(A)

Treatment applied: This review follows the PRISMA flow diagram, which consists of four stages: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion. At the identification stage, 114 articles (A) were sourced from the Scopus database. The search parameters included article titles, abstracts, and keywords. Subsequently, the abstracts of these 114 articles were manually screened for initial eligibility. Articles were retained if they: i) addressed biodiversity; ii) discussed business and its impact, and iii) contained economic & financial instruments implemented or to be implemented by governments (R2). This process resulted in 49 articles being selected (B). At the eligibility stage, the full texts of these 49 articles were assessed using the aforementioned three categories, focusing on inclusion of the measures of dependence and impact on biodiversity in developing policy instruments aimed at promoting business actions for biodiversity (R3). Finally, 20 papers (C) were selected and described in section 6.3 of Chapter 6 and summarized in Table 6.3 “Examples of policy instruments based on evidence for biodiversity management decision-making targeting businesses”.

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_6.3_07-2024_(A)	.csv	337 KB	114 papers obtained through the review
B	IPBES_BBA_6.3_07-2024_(B)	.csv	133 KB	49 papers obtained after abstract screening
C	IPBES_BBA_6.3_07-2024_(C)	.csv	59 KB	Final sample of 20 papers